

Investigating instrument identification in a virtual orchestral scene

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Abstract

Musical scene analysis (MSA) in an orchestral context is affected by the spatial positioning of instruments on stage, the reverberation of the concert hall, and the musical structure itself. Although studies have investigated the perceptual blending of instruments in musical mixtures, instrument identification has mostly been studied for sounds in isolation. How the acoustic and musical variables affect identification performance remains unclear. In the present study we used a cue-mixture identification paradigm to have participants identify eight sustained instruments in twelve short four-instrument mixtures taken from Wagner's *Tristan* prelude. Excerpts were rendered with and without concert hall acoustics using a room-acoustic modeling software with instruments either spread out on stage or all in a single center location. Against initial hypotheses, reverberation of the virtual concert hall and spatial distribution of instruments did not affect identification performance, despite clear effects on sound quality ratings. On the other hand, instrument-dependent musical effects of voice, register, and acoustical content were observed. These results hint at instrument identification performance showing robustness to variations in acoustic conditions and highlight the complex nature of instrument perception in realistic sound mixtures.

Keywords: instrument identification, musical mixture, room acoustics, virtual acoustics, timbre

Introduction

In music listening, the perception of the mixture of sounds from instruments playing simultaneously is impacted by a host of influencing factors. Imagine a listener sitting in a spacious concert hall with a large orchestra on stage playing a symphony. While the listener closes their eyes they may – or may not – pick up on the different instruments that make up the sound mixture. This picture already gives us a hint at what these influencing factors might be. Firstly, the instruments – as separate sound sources – are distributed on stage and the sound waves they produce reach the listener from different directions. Secondly, not only the direct sound is perceived by the listener. The walls (and ceiling) of the concert hall create reflections of the instruments' sound waves of which early ones overlap with the direct sound depending on the position of the listener. Later reflections add to a sense of space by creating reverberation inside the hall. Critically, not only the acoustic environment shapes the listener's perception but also the music itself. Changes in orchestration and the structured interplay of instruments affect what is audible – of course based on the listener's prior knowledge and experience with the music at hand.

Many studies have focused on the individual aspects that shape this sonic experience. It is well understood that the acoustics of concert halls shape the listener's perception (e.g., Beranek, 2012; Lokki and Pätynen, 2020). Concerning instrument perception, Goad and Keefe (1992) have shown that variations in the acoustic properties of performance spaces affect timbre discrimination. Kato et al. (2014) reported variations in perceived timbral brightness of clarinet tones when convolved with two varying binaural room impulse responses. In a recent study, effects of room acoustic parameters were explored in the perception of musical blending (Thilakan et al., 2025). Sounds of two violins with varying levels of source level blending were rendered in different room acoustic environments that differed in their volumetric size, absorption behavior, and listener position. The authors found

significant effects for all variables, with source level blending contributing 60% and room-acoustic parameters 40% to the prediction of subjective blend ratings using a random forest regression model. Together, these studies demonstrate the influence room acoustics can have on the perception of instrument sounds and music.

Another factor in our concert scenario is the placement of instruments on stage. Its influence on the parsing of individual sound sources can be described by auditory scene analysis (ASA; Bregman, 1990). In ASA, sound source separation is the key objective. This is governed by perceptual grouping mechanisms that are described by *Gestalt* psychology. Sound events that are similar and follow specific organization principles tend to be perceived as one item. Important principles include *proximity*, *closure*, *common fate*, and *continuity*. Most of these grouping principles are results of primitive (bottom-up) processing in the auditory system. There also exists schema-driven (top-down) processing based on prior knowledge, memory, and attention. Spatial distribution as a principle of ASA allows for better sound source separation, at least for synthetic sounds (van Noorden, 1975). Together with other factors influencing the grouping of sounds, it might not be as strong of a cue (Bregman, 1990). However, other studies on the spatial release from masking (e.g., Litovsky et al., 2021) do attribute spatial distribution as a relevant cue to scene parsing.

The third factor is the music itself. What becomes audible is governed by its orchestration and guided by ASA. In multi-source scenarios, simultaneous sounds from different instruments can be perceived as single fused entity (McAdams, 2019). This auditory fusion of instrument sounds is also called timbre blending and can lead to sounds with unique timbres (Sandell, 1995). Studies showed correlations of subjective blend ratings with acoustical descriptors such as energy maxima, spectral center of gravity, onset synchrony, but also crossing of voices and consonance (Reuter, 1996; Tardieu and McAdams, 2012; Lembke et al., 2017) – all of which are results of the individual instruments' sounds and their

orchestration. More recent studies investigated instrumental blends in complex orchestral excerpts and found several factors – score-based and acoustic – that influenced participants' blend and segregation ratings (Fischer et al., 2021; McAdams et al., 2025).

These aspects of instrument timbre and orchestral scene perception are mostly measured using subjective ratings scales that can be prone to bias. Another way to determine what a listener hears out from an orchestral mixture can be realized through an instrument identification task as an objective measure. By asking whether an instrument was in the mixture or not – or by directly asking for the specific instrument – one obtains a binary decision, which can either be correct or incorrect. This yields a simple measure that does not depend on a subjective rating scale.

Instrument identification as a perceptual listening task has already been studied extensively. In one of the first published studies, Eagleson and Eagleson (1947) claimed that identification of musical instruments is a rather “trivial” task. They had participants identify nine instruments directly and over a public address (PA) system. Identification accuracy was between 69% and 94% when heard directly and dropped by more than 10 percentage points when heard over the PA system (55% – 82%). Srinivasan et al. (2002) provided a baseline of identification performance by conservatory students using closed-sets of two, three, nine, and 27 instruments. Identification accuracies for the first three sets was very high with above 90% but dropped to around 56% for the large set of 27 instruments. There exist several other studies on instrument identification (Saldanha and Corso, 1964; Berger, 1964; Strong and Clark, 1967; Elliott, 1975), all of them reporting different overall identification accuracies for unaltered sounds in isolation. The selection and number of instruments to be identified and the varying expertise of participants (non-musicians, musicians) explain such differences. These early studies – but also recent ones – were concerned with the spectro-temporal ingredients that shape identification performance (Patil et al., 2012; Thoret et al., 2017;

Siedenburg, 2019; Siedenburg et al., 2019). Although stationary spectral envelopes of instruments' sounds are a major distinguishing factor, temporal features, such as, e.g. sounds' onsets also play a critical role in instrument identification. All of these studies, however, were constrained to instrument sounds in isolation. To our knowledge, there are no previous studies on instrument identification in sound mixtures. Hence, whether the found factors that affect identification in isolation are of similar importance in and generalize to instrument mixtures remains unclear. Furthermore, general aspects of room acoustics such as reverberation and spatial distribution have not yet been investigated in the light of instrument identification.

Thus, in the present study, we investigate instrument identification in a virtual acoustic environment by using a novel cue-mixture identification task. As source material we used a realistic simulated score from Richard Wagner's prelude to the Opera *Tristan und Isolde*. Participants were instructed to hear out and identify a single instrument from a mixture by being provided a melodic line as a cue from the mixture. To consider varying acoustic conditions that might affect identification abilities, we present the instrument mixtures with and without reverberation and with instruments spread out or all centered on a stage in a virtual acoustic scene rendered via a loudspeaker array.

Our focus on instrument identification was motivated not only by the need to extend the current state of research on identification to multi-source scenarios but also to complement findings on timbre blending. The extent to how well instruments blend is associated with their identifiability. Kendall and Carterette (1993) found that increasing blend correlated with decreasing identification in simultaneous orchestral wind instrument sounds. This inverse relationship of blend and identification was later formulated in more detail by Sandell (1995). Thus, an identification task could provide an objective way to capture blend ratings. Besides

the identification task, we also gathered sound quality ratings to assess the acoustic changes to the virtual scene qualitatively and provide a comparison for the audibility of these changes.

Method

This experiment consists of the main instrument identification task and a sound quality rating task to compare the quantitative identification results with qualitative measures.

Participants

The experiment had 21 participants. All participants were recruited through the online job board of the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg with the prerequisites of self-reported normal hearing and at least five years of continuous professional training on a musical instrument. The participants had a mean age of 25.0 years ($SD = 3.3$). In addition to the experiment, the participants had to complete two questionnaires on their musical perception and training abilities based on the Goldsmith Musical Sophistication Index (Gold-MSI, Müllensiefen et al., 2014) The average scores were 4.69 out of 7 ($SD = 1.84$) for the perception questionnaire and 4.53 out of 7 ($SD = 1.96$) for the training questionnaire.

Stimuli and task

The stimuli consisted of short excerpts from the prelude to the opera *Tristan und Isolde* by Richard Wagner. A synthesized multitrack stereo mix from the *OrchPlay Music Library* (www.orchestraplayer.com) was used. It features hybrid instrument recordings of individual notes that were used to create a realistic mix with particular detail to intonation, dynamics, tempo, and blend between instruments. These features were hand-sculpted by a composer with a doctorate in music composition (co-author FB). The synthesized mix contained individual single-note instrument recordings from two sound libraries: the Berlin series from *Orchestral Tools* (OT) and the *Vienna Symphonic Library* (VSL). Both libraries do not

provide anechoic stimuli and there are differences in the level of dryness in the individual synthesized instrument tracks.

Figure 1: (A) cue-mixture identification task. (B) Simplified overview of the dimensions of the shoebox-sized virtual concert hall in TASCAR and the orchestral seating configuration. Instruments used in the identification task are color-coded, additional full orchestration (sound quality rating task) in white. Connecting lines between the individual string sections visualize the stereo panning. The centered dashed circle corresponds to the positioning of instruments in the center condition.

The identification task consisted of a cue and a mixture containing a target instrument, as visualized in Figure 1A. The sinusoidal cue provided tonal information repeated by the target instrument in the mixture. Participants were then asked *Which instrument played the cued melody*. As of our knowledge, no studies on instrument identification have used such a cue-mixture paradigm. Previous studies on musical pattern or instrument detection have used a target-in-mixture approach (Bey and McAdams, 2002; Bürgel et al., 2021) where a target pattern or instrument had to be detected within a mixture of patterns or instruments – with the target being presented either before or after the mixture. This approach results in a binary Y/N decision. Although our identification task was not a binary decision because it involved more than two instruments, we extracted a binary scoring (correct, incorrect) for identification results. Other approaches of asking participants what instruments they heard in the mixture would not strictly result in such a binary scoring and would require a criterion for correct or incorrect labels of responses for mixtures with multiple instruments. Hence, we opted for the more streamlined and novel cue-mixture paradigm, essentially requiring two perceptual processes: the matching of the pitch information of the target in the mixture and the subsequent (or even parallel) identification of the instrument.

The *Toolbox for auditory scene creation and rendering* (TASCAR; Grimm et al., 2019) was used for rendering the orchestral scene in a virtual acoustic environment. The toolbox has been used in many auditory listening studies (e.g., Gerken et al., 2014; Hendrikse et al., 2019). TASCAR uses a mirror source model for the early reflections and a feedback-delay network for diffuse late reverberation. The *Sendesaal Bremen*, Germany, was used as a concert hall model. It features individual angled wall elements while resembling the physical specifications a shoebox-shaped hall. Concert halls of this type are considered among the best concert halls in the world (Beranek, 2012) and comparatively straight-forward from the perspective of virtual acoustic simulation. The damping and reflection parameters of the

virtual hall were tweaked which resulted in a reverberation time (RT) of 1.9 seconds. The instruments were placed across the stage in a symphonic setting. The woodwinds, brass and timpani all featured individual mono sound sources. For the strings (first violin, second violins, violas, cellos, and double basses), which feature tutti sounds and not individual sources, the left and right channels of the tracks were placed in such a way to create a realistic impression of a section of instruments. Exact placements of the instruments and specifications of the shoebox-shaped hall are shown in Figure 1B. Acoustical playback was realized in a semi-anechoic room using an array of 16 loudspeakers (Genelec 8030B). Nearest speaker panning was chosen as playback method. In addition to the source material not being anechoic, the sound sources do not feature instrument-specific and frequency-dependent directivity patterns (Meyer, 2008) but are represented as spherical sources. Furthermore, natural movement of the players is not considered (Ackermann et al., 2024). This being said, it is to be noted that any study of musical scene perception in orchestral music faces a tradeoff between the quality of the musical source material, the amount of control on individual tracks and instruments, and the realism of the acoustical rendering, because these factors are intertwined in reality.

Twelve short excerpts were chosen from the original score for the identification task. Instead of using the complete mixture each excerpt only consisted of four instruments. A preliminary pilot of the experiment with the full mixture in the context of the identification of a single cued instrument proved to be a task beyond the intended level of difficulty. A total of eight exemplary instruments were used: flute, oboe, English horn, clarinet, bassoon, French horn, cellos, and violins, as seen in Figure 1A. These instruments were chosen to feature instruments that appear continuously across the score while belonging to either group of woodwinds, brass, and strings. The pairings of oboe and English horn were chosen to evaluate participants' abilities to differentiate between these instruments of similar physical

shape and sound. Also, the English horn plays a prominent role in the prelude to *Tristan und Isolde*. Figure 2 shows the musical notation of each instrument part for the twelve excerpts. A list of the excerpts including their type, orchestration, and duration is included in the supplementary materials (see Table 1).

Table 1: Instruments (number of appearances across excerpts) used in the identification task, their abbreviations (short), and class belonging.

Instrument	Short	Class
Flute (4)	fl	woodwind
Oboe (6)	ob	woodwind
English Horn (7)	eh	woodwind
Clarinet (7)	cl	woodwind
Bassoon (8)	bn	woodwind
French Horn (9)	hn	brass
Violins (4)	vn	string
Cellos (3)	vc	string

Figure 2: Twelve short excerpts from Richard Wagner's prelude to the opera *Tristan und Isolde* used for the identification task of the experiment. Instruments are color-coded and sorted along voices (voices one and two in the upper staff line, voices three and four in the lower staff line).

Procedure

The experiment consisted of three main sessions: a familiarization and training session, an identification session, and a sound quality rating session. For the familiarization participants could freely cycle through the playback of a shared melodic line for all instruments until they felt comfortable to continue with the experiment. The isolated instruments lines were played back through the center speaker without reverb. A short training session ensued in which participants had to correctly identify each instrument within a mixture of four in the context of the cue-mixture paradigm. The mixture was played back with all instruments coming from

the front speaker in the center with reverberation on. Training trials with an incorrect response were repeated until correct identification. Feedback as *correct* or *incorrect* was given. After the training session the main identification task followed. Each excerpt was repeated for all four instruments within the mixture and for the combination of the conditions of reverb (on or off) and the spatial distribution of instruments (spread or center). This resulted in a total of distinct 192 trials for the identification task. The trial order was pseudo-randomized to avoid direct repetition of excerpts. No feedback was given for correct or incorrect answers as participants would be able to learn the orchestration of the fixed four-instrument mixtures. For both, the training and test session, the cue was not affected by the acoustic condition, as it was always presented through the front speaker in the center outside of the virtual orchestral scene in TASCAR. In the last session, participants were asked to give their subjective ratings of the attributes of naturalism, fullness, and width of the sound for ten extended excerpts with full orchestration. Furthermore, they were asked whether the rendering sounded like being in a concert hall and how they liked the sound overall. All five ratings were given on a 7-point Likert scale. The individual attributes and rating scales are given in Table 2 and a list of the extended excerpts including measures, dynamics, duration, and orchestration is included in the supplementary materials (see Table 2). Each excerpt was played four times with the combinations of the conditions for reverb and spatial distribution, resulting in a total of 40 trials. At the end of the experiment, participants were asked to complete the questionnaires on musical perception and training abilities.

Table 2: Sound attributes, questions, and rating scales for the sound quality rating task.

Attribute	Questions	Rating scale
Transparency	How artificial/natural was the sound?	very artificial –very natural
Sonority	How thin/full was the sound?	very thin – very full
Spatiality	How narrow/wide was the sound?	very narrow – very wide
Concert hall	The sound feels like being in a concert hall.	disagree completely – agree completely
Overall	Overall, how much did you like the sound?	very bad – very good

Data analysis

For the statistical analysis of the identification task, binomial generalized linear mixed-effect models (GLMMs) were used (West et al., 2022). All models were computed in R using the *lme4* package (Bates et al., 2015). If not specified differently, all models included by-participant, by-excerpt, and by-instrument intercepts as random effects. All categorical predictors were sum-coded. For the sound quality data analysis, a similar approach was done using separate linear mixed-effect models (LMM) for each rating scale. As random effects, the models included by-participant and by-excerpt intercepts; as fixed effects, the models included the predictors of reverberation (off, on), spatial distribution (center, spread), and their interaction terms. All predictors were sum-coded. Full model results for both GLMMs and LMMs are included in the supplementary materials (see Tables 4–18). Further, we used the *librosa* package (McFee et al., 2024) in Python for a subsequent analysis of timbral features describing acoustic similarity. Audio files were sampled at 24 kHz sampling rate and features were extracted from non-overlapping RMS-weighted windows of 100 ms duration.

Figure 3: Instrument identification results. Error bars indicate bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals. Dashed lines indicate chance level at 0.125. Smaller round dots correspond to binned individual participant means. (A) Instrument and overall identification accuracy. (B) Confusion matrix for the target and identified instruments with darker colors corresponding to higher proportions. (C) Acoustic conditions as interactions of spatial distribution (center, spread) and reverberation (off, on). (D) Voice order (approximation) within excerpts (4: lowest voice, 1: highest voice). (E) Instruments' low, middle, and high register.

Results

Instrument Identification

Instrument identification was measured for short, four-instrument mixtures using a cued target-mixture paradigm. Figure 3A depicts the instrument and overall identification accuracy. Overall, identification accuracy was 0.36 [0.32 0.40] with a range (participant level) of 0.20–0.52. This is well above chance level of 0.125. The instrument data were analyzed using a binomial GLMM. As random effects, the model included by-participant and

by-measure intercepts but no by-instrument intercept. As fixed effect, the model included the predictor of instrument. The model results confirmed that there was a main effect of target instrument ($\chi^2 = 269.30$, $p < .001$), that is, there were significant differences in identification accuracy between individual instruments. Where the violins ($M = 0.65$ [0.56, 0.73]), flute ($M = 0.59$ [0.50, 0.67]), and cellos ($M = 0.54$ [0.44, 0.63]) showed the highest accuracies, other woodwinds were below average with the lowest accuracy for the oboe ($M = 0.18$ [0.13, 0.23]), but still above chance. A full overview of identification accuracies across excerpt and instrument are included in the supplementary materials (see Table 3).

Figure 3B depicts the confusion matrix for the identification task. Columns represent the true target instruments and rows represent the identified instruments. The matrix is normalized by column to indicate the proportion of identifications for each target instrument. The diagonal reflects the correct identifications and corresponds to the accuracy values in Figure 1A. Off-diagonal entries represent confusions between individual instruments and within instrument groups. Strong confusion occurred for most woodwinds (oboe, English horn, clarinet) with the oboe being misidentified as an English horn more often than correctly identified. Also, the bassoon showed moderate confusion with the oboe, English horn, and clarinet. Only the flute, belonging to the woodwinds, broke this pattern and was mostly confused with the sound of the French horn. The French horn was in turn confused with the bassoon. There was also confusion among the strings where cellos were strongly confused with the violins, but the violins only occasionally with the cellos. Overall, these results highlight strong variability in identification accuracy across instruments.

Focus of this work were possible influences of spatial distribution of instruments on stage (center/spread) and the reverberation of the virtual concert hall (off/on) on the identification performance. Figure 3C depicts the identification accuracy across acoustic condition as the interactions of spatial distribution and reverberation. Surprisingly, there are no visible

differences between the acoustic conditions. The acoustic data were analyzed using a binomial GLMM with the predictors of spatial distribution (center, spread), reverberation (off, on), and their interaction term as fixed effects ($R^2_{cond} = .20$, $R^2_{marg} = .00$). The model results confirmed no main effect of spatial distribution and reverberation ($\chi^2 = 5.39$, $p = .145$) with the marginal means center/off: $M = 0.38$ [0.25, 0.52], center/on: $M = 0.36$ [0.24, 0.50], spread/off: $M = 0.37$ [0.25, 0.51], spread/on: $M = 0.41$ [0.28, 0.56]. There was, however, a marginal interaction effect ($\beta = 0.06$ [-0.03, 0.49], $p = .078$), reflected in the increased identification accuracy in the spread/on condition. These results show that – against initial hypotheses – instrument identification performance was robust to variability in the virtual acoustic conditions.

Figure 4: Training effect on participants' identification performance as identification accuracy across trial number on a logarithmic axis. Thin continuous lines depict the moving averages (10-trial window) including 95% confidence intervals as shaded areas. Thick dashed lines depict the fixed effects from the model output of a GLMM including 95% confidence intervals as shaded areas.

We also investigated a possible training effect on the participants' identification performance. Figure 4 depicts the mean identification accuracy across participants over the time course

(trial number) of the experiment on a logarithmic axis as moving averages (10-trial window). Over all trials (and conditions), identification accuracy increased with increasing trial number. Within the different acoustic conditions, the time course varied. The time course data were analyzed using a binomial GLMM with the predictors of trial number (scaled), spatial distribution (center, spread), reverberation (off, on) and their (three-way) interactions as fixed effects ($R^2_{cond} = .22$, $R^2_{marg} = .02$). The extracted fixed effects are overlaid in Figure 4 as dashed thick lines. The model results confirmed a main effect of trial number ($\beta = 0.17$ [0.10, 0.25], $p < .001$). That is, participants improved in the identification task over the course of the experiment. Although two-way interactions between trial number and spatial distribution or reverberation, respectively, showed no effect ($\beta < -0.01$, $p > .058$), the three-way interaction term was significant ($\beta = -0.15$ [-0.22, -0.07], $p < .001$). However, these results are difficult to interpret. It seems that the condition with no reverberation and instruments distributed across stage led to the strongest increase in identification accuracy over time. Likewise, its inverse with instruments at a center location and the presence of reverberation also showed a strong increase. Curiously, both conditions showed lower initial accuracies compared to the “realistic” acoustic condition, with instruments distributed and reverberation on, as of their moving averages and the model fit. The most “unrealistic” condition (instruments spread, reverb off) also showed low accuracies over the first 30 trials, but the fixed effect extracted from the model seems to flatline.

Since each mixture consisted of four instruments, the excerpts were ordered by voice from highest (voice one) to lowest (voice four) – although not all voice configurations were clear due to the crossing of voices. Figure 3D shows the mean identification accuracy across voice from lowest to highest in terms of pitch height. Identification accuracy for outer voices (voice one: $M = 0.44$ [0.41, 0.46]; voice four: $M = 0.38$ [0.35, 0.41]) stood out from the inner voices (voice two: $M = 0.33$ [0.30, 0.36]; voice three: $M = 0.29$ [0.26, 0.31]). The voice data were

analyzed using a binomial GLMM. As fixed effects, the model included the predictor of voice as linear and quadratic terms ($R^2_{cond} = .19$, $R^2_{marg} = .01$). The model confirmed that there was a main effect of voice, both as linear ($\beta = -0.90 [-1.35, -0.45]$, $p < .001$) and quadratic terms ($\beta = 0.17 [0.08, 0.25]$, $p < .001$). That is, identification accuracy was affected considerably by the target instruments' note positions within the mixture. However, there was great variability in identification accuracy across target instruments – as already seen in the overall and instrument identification performance. Random effects variance in the model for the target instruments was 0.48, considerably larger than the variances for participants (0.18) and excerpts (0.11). This justifies a closer look at the orchestration for each measure.

Figure 5: Mean identification accuracy for each instrument per excerpt as filled markers across voices 3 within the excerpt. Error bars indicate bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals. Smaller empty markers indicate the top confused instrument if identification of the target instrument was below chance level (0.125). Transparent bars correspond to the acoustic conditions as interactions of spatial distribution and reverberation in the order center/off, center/on, spread/off, and spread/on.

Figure 5 shows identification accuracies for mixture instruments in each excerpt across voice. Error bars indicate the 95% CIs and transparent bars correspond to the underlying accuracies for the interactions of spatial distribution and reverberation. Overall, there is substantial variability in accuracy per excerpt and instrument. Some excerpts exhibit the previously analyzed effect of the outer voices (excerpts M12, M41, M56, M74), some show a flat (M2, M10) or mixed trend, and others even display an inverse effect (M16, M34), where the

middle voices are more accurately identified. Furthermore, the plot shows the top confused instrument if its identification accuracy was above that of the correct target instrument.

Depending on the voice within the excerpt, instruments were often confused with their lower counterparts, such as, e.g. the oboe in voice three with the English horn (M6, M10) or the cellos in the second voice with the violins (M72). Although spatial distribution of instruments and reverberation did not have an overall effect on the identification performance, individual trends can be seen from the transparent bars for each instrument (Fig. 5) reflecting the acoustic configuration instruments center/reverb off, center/on, spread/off, and spread/on. Cellos always benefited when being presented at their expected position on the right of the stage, opposite from the violins (M56, M72, M74). When both string instruments appeared in the same excerpt (M72) also the violins showed this improvement from spatial distribution. In the center condition, the accuracies were substantially lower. Other instruments were affected by reverberation as seen, e.g., for the French horn (M10, M72), where added reverberation led to an increase in identification accuracy. Other instruments showed mixed effects, and the flute seemed to be unaffected from the acoustic conditions. Again, these results highlight the strong variability individual instrument sounds impose on participants' identification performance.

Additionally, a possible effect of instruments' F0-register was investigated since it can strongly affect an instrument's timbre. We argued that identification accuracy in instruments' middle register is higher as participants would be more familiar with more “common” sounds. Figure 3E shows the identification accuracy for low, middle, and high F0-registers. Mean identification accuracies indeed varied between the registers with the middle register showing the highest identification accuracy. Based on the given excerpt, not all instruments' registers were represented. Low register included oboe, clarinet, and French horn, middle register included all instruments except the clarinet, and high register included flute, oboe,

clarinet, bassoon, and cellos. A binomial GLMM was used to analyze the effect of instrument register on the identification accuracy. As a fixed effect, the model included the predictor of register as a factor with the levels *low*, *middle*, and *high*. The model confirmed that there was a significant effect of register ($\chi^2 = 60.07, p < .001$) even if the target instruments were included as random effects. Identification accuracy was significantly higher in the middle register at 0.47 [0.33, 0.61]. Marginal means for the low and high register were 0.23 [0.14, 0.36] and 0.30 [0.19, 0.44]. This result shows that instrument register did affect participants' instrument identification performance, likely due to a higher familiarity with sounds from instruments' middle registers.

We also checked whether the register effect was a pseudo effect as a result of an underlying effect of pitch on a global level. For this, we computed a binomial GLMM with the predictor of pitch as linear and quadratic terms as well as their interaction. We did find an effect of pitch ($\chi^2 = 162.15, p < .001$) as linear ($\beta = -0.39 [-0.59, -0.19], p < .001$), quadratic ($\beta = 0.12 [0.03, 0.21], p < .01$), and interaction terms ($\beta = 0.28 [0.23, 0.34], p < .001$). It even outperformed the register model ($\chi^2 = 102.08, p < .001$), that is, pitch explained more variance in identification accuracy than register. However, when combining both register and pitch (linear, quadratic, and interaction terms) as fixed effects in a single model, in turn, it outperformed the pitch model ($\chi^2 = 58.79, p < .001$). Overall, although pitch (on a global level) is a better predictor for identification accuracy than register (on instrument level), the effect of register remains significant even after accounting for pitch.

We investigated a potential relationship of identification and the acoustic similarity between instrument sounds. For each isolated instrument within a mixture of an excerpt, we extracted spectral centroid (SC) as a measure of the spectral center of gravity, spectral flux (SF) as a measure of spectral changes over time, and Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs, coefficients no. 2-13) as a measure of coarse spectral shape from 100 ms analysis windows.

We conducted comparisons between the target and all three other instruments within each mixture by computing the average SC heights of target-instrument pairs, the Pearson correlation coefficient of their SF time series, and the mean of the Pearson correlation coefficients of their MFCC time series. For each target instrument, we computed two summary statistics per feature: the mean value across all three possible pairings, and the extreme value (minimum for average SC height, maximum for SF and MFCC correlations). That is, we compared the acoustic similarity of a specific instrument to either the average across all other mixture instruments (“average model”) or only the single most similar one within that mixture (“single model”). We then used two separate GLMMs with average SC height, SF correlation, and MFCC correlation as fixed effects predictors, as well as participant, excerpt, and target instrument as random effects to predict identification accuracy. Both models showed significant effects of all feature summary statistics (average model: $\chi^2 = 128.71$, $p < .001$; single model: $\chi^2 = 101.99$, $p < .001$), with the average model ($R^2_{cond} = .50$, $R^2_{marg} = .20$) describing more variance than the single model ($R^2_{cond} = .44$, $R^2_{marg} = .20$). There was a significant effect of average SC height in both models (average: $\beta = 0.86$ [0.61, 1.11], $p < .001$; single: $\beta = 0.66$ [0.46, 0.88], $p < .001$). That is, identification accuracy indeed increased with increasing average SC height. Also, SF showed significant effects in both models (average: $\beta = -0.76$ [-0.96, -0.55], $p < .001$; single: $\beta = -0.75$ [-0.97, -0.53], $p < .001$). That is, identification accuracy decreased with increasing SF correlation. MFCC correlation showed a significant effect in the average model ($\beta = -0.31$ [-0.45, -0.17], $p < .001$) but only a marginal effect in the single model ($\beta = -0.21$ [-0.38, -0.05], $p = .011$). That is, identification accuracy decreased with increasing MFCC correlation. Overall, these results show that acoustic similarity between the target and mixture instruments captured a substantial amount of variance seen in the identification data.

Figure 6: Sound quality ratings across acoustic condition for the rating scales sonority, spatiality, and overall, with binned individual participant ratings and bootstrapped 95% confidence intervals as error bars.

Sound quality

Sound quality ratings of longer full-mixture excerpts were gathered using five 7-point Likert rating scales for room-acoustic and overall attributes of the sound. All rating scales were analyzed using individual LMMs. The conditional and marginal statistics for the five models were *transparency*: $R^2_{cond} = .23$, $R^2_{marg} = .07$; *sonority*: $R^2_{cond} = .41$, $R^2_{marg} = .11$; *spatiality*: $R^2_{cond} = .35$, $R^2_{marg} = .21$; *concert hall*: $R^2_{cond} = .32$, $R^2_{marg} = .16$; *overall*: $R^2_{cond} = .26$, $R^2_{marg} = .12$.

Based on a Pearson correlation analysis on the residuals of each model the scales showed moderate to strong correlations between each other (Pearson's $r(838) > .44$, $p < .001$). Since the *overall* rating was strongly correlated with both the *concert* ($r = .73$) and *transparency* rating ($r = .70$), only the *overall*, *sonority* and *spatiality* ratings are analyzed in detail.

Nonetheless, all five models showed main effects of reverberation ($\beta > 0.21$, $p < .001$) and spatial distribution ($\beta > 0.35$, $p < .001$). Also, their interaction effects were significant ($\beta < -0.16$, $p < .002$).

Figure 6 shows the sound quality ratings across acoustic conditions for the *sonority*, *spatiality*, and *overall* rating scales. Results for the *transparency* and *concert hall* rating scales are included in the supplementary materials (see Figure 1). Mean *sonority* ratings (*How thin/full was the sound?*) in each condition were above neutral, indicating that the sound was generally perceived as full. A significant effect of both reverberation ($\beta = 0.32$ [0.29, 0.46], $p < .001$) and spatial distribution ($\beta = 0.37$ [0.24, 0.41], $p < .001$) individually lead to a strong increase in ratings ($M = 5.20$; $M = 5.16$) compared to the center and reverb off condition ($M = 4.07$). Their interaction, however, did not increase the ratings much further (spread/on: $M = 5.35$). For the *spatiality* ratings (*How narrow/wide was the sound?*) the picture is a bit different. Spatial distribution had the strongest effect ($\beta = 0.73$ [0.63, 0.83], $p < .001$) with a large increase in ratings from center/off ($M = 3.42$) to spread/off ($M = 5.27$) indicating the perception of the sound to be wider. However, also reverberation had a significant but smaller effect on the perceived width ($\beta = 0.30$ [0.20, 0.39], $p < .001$). Again, the interaction of spatial distribution and reverberation did not lead to an additional increase in ratings ($M = 5.43$). The *overall* ratings (*Overall, how much did you like the sound?*) showed similar effects of reverberation ($\beta = 0.21$ [0.12, 0.30], $p < .001$) and spatial distribution ($\beta = 0.42$ [0.33, 0.50], $p < .001$) leading to increases in ratings for the center/on ($M = 4.61$) and spread/off ($M = 4.97$) conditions compared to the center/off conditions ($M = 3.75$). Like for the other scales, there was no further increase in ratings for the spread/on condition ($M = 4.97$).

Besides the main effects of reverberation and spatial distribution, musical effects of excerpt, dynamics, and orchestration were analyzed. Effects of excerpt were seen for all ratings scales ($\chi^2 > 35.26$, $p < .001$). Especially the *sonority* ratings differed from excerpt to excerpt ($\chi^2 = 209.37$, $p < .001$). This excerpt dependence can be attributed to changes in dynamic playing level. Namely, effects of dynamics were seen for the *sonority* ratings ($\chi^2 = 21.80$, $p < .001$),

the *spatiality* ratings ($\chi^2 = 10.55, p = .005$), and for the *concert* ratings ($\chi^2 = 10.49, p = .005$). For all three rating scales, excerpts with an overall playing level of *piano* were rated less full ($\beta = -1.12 [-1.41, -0.83], p < .001$), wide ($\beta = -0.49 [-0.73, -0.23], p = .007$), and sounding like being in a concert hall ($\beta = -0.30 [-0.83, -0.25], p = .009$), respectively. For the *sonority* ratings, excerpts with an overall playing level *fortissimo* were rated as fuller ($\beta = 1.02 [0.72, 1.31], p < .001$). We did not find any effects of orchestration as number of instruments playing on the sound quality ratings.

These results show that participants were well able to distinguish perceptually between the different acoustic conditions. The lack of effects of acoustic conditions on instrument identification thus should be interpreted as a sign of the robustness of this task to acoustical manipulations, rather than a lack of effectiveness of these manipulations in the present experiment.

Discussion

We used a cue-mixture closed-set instrument identification task to evaluate the identification performance of musically trained participants with short four-instrument mixtures from Richard Wagner's prelude to the opera *Tristan und Isolde* across different acoustic conditions in a virtual acoustic scene. The conditions varied in spatial distribution (center/spread) of instruments on stage and reverberation (off/on) in the virtual concert hall. Furthermore, participants rated longer excerpts with full orchestration in each acoustic condition using five sound quality rating scales.

Overall, the cue-mixture paradigm proved to be challenging for the participants but not too difficult as the overall identification accuracy of 0.36 was well above chance at 0.125. There was a moderate correlation between participants' mean identification accuracy and their average Gold-MSI score ($R^2 = .41, p = .002$), that is, participants with higher average Gold-

MSI scores performed better on the identification task. A visual representation is included in the supplementary materials (see Figure 3). Furthermore, we saw an overall training effect on participants' identification performance. Identification accuracies increased over the time course of the experiment with some evidence for varying slopes across acoustic conditions.

Room-acoustic effects

Our identification results indicated that there were no clear effects of spatial distribution nor reverberation on the identification performance. This is surprising and against our initial hypotheses. It is known from ASA that sound source separation works better if the sources are separated in space (Bregman, 1990) – although Bregman also states that the strength of this cue diminishes with the presence of other influencing factors. In a study on musical scene analysis abilities, Hake et al. (2003) found a modest effect of spatial separation through changes in stereo width of up to 180 degrees in a task in which listeners were asked to hear out target sounds in a musical mixture. We hypothesized that a clear separation of instrument sources through spatial distribution on a stage – although only at a maximum of around 60 degrees and thus much narrower than 180 degrees stereo width – would also improve their identification. However, our results showed no significant effect of spatial distribution. Only when looking at individual excerpts and instruments some trends appeared. For instance, participants seemed to benefit from the spatial separation of violins and cellos, improving their identification performance especially when both instruments appeared in the same excerpt. However, this effect could also be attributed to the participants' prior or learned knowledge of a classical orchestral seating order with violins on the left and cellos on the right side of the stage.

With respect to reverberation, studies have reported influences on timbre perception. Goad and Keefe (1992) found instrument-dependent effects of differences in the early reflection sequence of room impulse responses on timbre discrimination. Constrained to clarinet sounds, Kato et al. (2014) saw strong effects of room-acoustic condition on timbral brightness ratings. Although we did see some differences in identification accuracies within instruments, which could be a result of alterations in timbre discrimination, overall, instrument identification seemed to be unaffected by the room-acoustic condition. Culling et al. (2003) showed that reverberation impaired listeners abilities to segregate competing voices from differences in F0 and spatial location. Although their findings were concerned with speech, one could argue that similar effects would be expected for tracking musical voices. Our results, however, do not support this view, at least for the identification of instruments in a sound mixture. One could argue that our cue-mixture paradigm facilitates a sort of attentional tracking (Woods & McDermott, 2015; Siedenburg et al., 2021), although correct identification of the target instrument would not necessarily require complete tracking of the cue. Short glimpses of individual notes and their timbral characteristics might be enough to form a decision, especially in trained musicians. Siedenburg et al. (2020) had found evidence in favor of glimpse-based processing in timbre discrimination, which was especially pronounced for young normal-hearing individuals fully able to use the available auditory cues.

In summary, our results suggest that cued instrument identification in four-instrument musical mixtures was robust to variations in acoustic conditions, as neither spatial distribution nor reverberation had significant effects on listeners' identification performance. It remains to be seen whether these results generalize to other cases of instrument identification with other task designs and musical structures.

Musical effects

Besides the room-acoustic effects, inherent musical effects of the excerpts and orchestration were seen. Our results showed an effect of voice within the excerpt. Instruments at the outer voices – lowest and highest – were identified more accurately than the two middle voices. In a recent study, Bürgel et al. (2024) found a similar effect for edge frequencies in an auditory pattern recognition paradigm with randomized pure tone melodies. The authors argued that auditory salience is driven by the relative, edge frequency positions. Our current results suggest that this effect could be extended towards the general perception of instrument sounds or melodies in a mixture.

Our results also showed that there was a significant effect of instruments' F0-register. Identification accuracy was significantly higher when target instruments played in their respective middle F0-registers. Likely, participants were more familiar with sounds from instruments' middle registers which eases identification compared to the high and low F0-registers. McAdams et al. (2023) found F0-register effects on identification of sustained and percussive instruments for participants' abilities to generalize across an instrument's entire range based on a single note or constrained arpeggios. We did, however, also see an effect of pitch on a global level. Jacobsen and Siedenburg (2024) also found a global effect of pitch for subjective ratings of sound pleasantness of synthesized instrument sounds, where ratings followed an inverted U-shape. For the present objective identification results, this pitch effect could possibly be explained by a stronger pitch clarity or increased toneness in the middle range of pitches (Huron, 2001) which might also ease identification. Overall, although pitch seemed to affect identification accuracies globally, register remained a significant predictor, as listeners benefitted from potential stronger familiarity with instruments' middle F0-registers.

Confusion of instruments at chance level can also be attributed to an effect of instrument register – in this case the register it occupies within an instrument class or family. For

example, in excerpt M6, the oboe in the third voice was strongly confused with the English horn. In excerpt M10, the clarinet in the top voice was confused with the oboe. In excerpt M72, the cellos in voice two were strongly confused with the violins. But also, across instrument families, confusions connected to instrument register occurred. In M56, the bassoon in the second voice was confused with the violins. All of these confusions can be – not solely – attributed to an effect of instrument register and participants' expectancies of what voice – or register – instruments occupy in a musical mixture. Of course, spectral similarities between instrument sounds – especially in the violins and cellos – also explain such confusions, but then again, these similarities allow for increased confusion based on register expectations. Put differently, both effects should be viewed in conjunction, with timbral similarities between instruments affecting instrument register perception. However, further experiments and analyses are needed to substantiate this notion.

Another factor explaining at chance level confusions is blending between instruments. The most prominent cases can be found in excerpts M34 and M72. In both excerpts, the top voice was confused with a lower voice – the French horn – playing the same note one octave apart. Since octave unison is a contender for increased blend between instruments sounds – apart from a stronger effect by perfect unison – and only one instrument was confused rather than both, these two measures could be an example of what is called an *augmented blend*, where one instrument's timbre is accentuated by a different instrument. This makes the former instrument stand out and the latter fall back in the mixture.

Results from two GLMMs incorporating the same timbral features that describe acoustic similarity (average SC heights, SF correlations, and MFCC correlations) shared significant variance with participants' identification performance. Coherent with the literature (Tardieu & McAdams, 2012), a higher average SC was associated with improved identification. Moreover, stronger correlations of SF and MFCC indicating similarities in the spectro-

temporal evolution between a given target instrument and the other instruments in the mixture were associated with reduced identification performance. As both models explain a substantial amount of variance seen in the data – compared to very little variance explained by the acoustic manipulations – we can conclude that differences in identification accuracy across instruments largely depend on the acoustic content of the source material. Although it is difficult to compare our acoustic similarity findings with subjective ratings of blend, we can speculate that our results partially support the conclusions of previous studies that investigated the relationship between instrument identification and blended instrument pairings (Kendall & Carterette, 1993; Sandell, 1995). These studies used simple instrument dyads at unison and major/minor thirds apart to find timbral descriptors that link blend and identification. The present findings may extend this notion towards more complex musical mixtures, even though this question should be re-addressed in follow-up studies with yet more controlled and possibly more rigid mixture designs alongside ratings of subjective blend.

In summary, instruments in the outer voices – although excerpt dependent – are identified more accurately than instruments in the inner voices, and effects of instrument register and blend explain confusions in most excerpts. Statistical analyses of timbral features to describe acoustic similarity showed substantial effects on identification performance and might help to support and extend previous literature on the blend-identification relationship to more complex musical mixtures.

Limitations and future directions

This study addresses instrument identification under realistic acoustic conditions. This entails the inclusion of multiple factors. Nowadays, virtual acoustic scenes using room-acoustic simulation tools provide environments to investigate auditory perception, not only for speech

but also music. Rendering of higher-order early reflections by geometrical considerations (e.g., use of mirror sound sources) produce physically accurate models of concert hall acoustics. However, this usually requires the use of anechoic recordings of musical instruments to accurately render reflections on the direct sound path. In our case, the multi-track recordings were not anechoic. This could lead to spectral alterations and changes in timbre, masking of onset transients, and smearing of the spatial cues. However, this might be less pronounced for sustained instrument sounds than for percussive sounds with sharper onsets. Furthermore, musical instruments have individual complex directivity patterns (Meyer, 2008). That is, the direct sound does not radiate outwards in a purely spherical pattern. Measured directivity patterns were found to be highly dependent on the dynamic playing level, the pitch produced by the instrument, the observed frequency band, and movements by the musicians (Ackermann et al., 2024).

In a symphonic orchestral setting, woodwind and brass instruments are usually solo instruments, that is, they play individual parts. In contrast, the strings (e.g. violins, cellos) mostly play in unison as one section to create a tutti sound. The multi-track sounds used in our study did not include individual instrument sources for the string sections. In an ideal setting, each instrument in their section would be represented as an individual sound source. However, this also results in a loss of source-level blending between the individual instruments. To simulate the auditory width of an entire violin section, we took the left and right channels of the stereo sound and placed them separately on the virtual stage to create a panned impression.

Another issue might be the unbalanced set of instruments to be identified, a consequence of using natural stimuli. Our selection of excerpts did not result in an equal distribution of instruments, that is, e.g. excerpts with French horn were overrepresented, those with cellos

underrepresented. Yet, this imbalance was accounted statistically for by including random by-instrument intercepts in our GLMMs.

Although our manipulations to the acoustic scene were clearly audible – as reflected in the sound quality ratings – the extent to which these “realistic” acoustic conditions affected identification performance might be underexplored; more extreme manipulations to the spatial configuration and reverberation might provide a clearer picture and help consolidate our notion of robustness of instrument identification to acoustic variations. Such extreme manipulations could entail spatial separation of instruments of up to 180 degrees (or even more) and comparisons of anechoic source material with reverberation times of well over two seconds.

Furthermore, our task design might have affected participants’ susceptibility to the acoustic variations. The identification paradigm was based on hearing out a musical cue from the mixture and subsequently naming the instrument that played said cue. Future studies could also incorporate a different task in which participants simply have to name all instruments they heard in the mixture. This approach would help disentangle possible conflicts of task design and acoustic cue relevance.

Since our results showed strong differences in identification accuracy across instruments and random variance explained by target instrument was high, a follow-up study using controlled musical stimuli should be conducted. In this way, the hierarchy effect of certain instruments based on their voice within excerpts – as a direct result of orchestration practices – could be avoided. Furthermore, analyses using spectro-temporal features should be used to further investigate the present musical effects to ideally construct a computational model of instrument identification in complex musical mixtures.

Conclusion

A novel cue-mixture task was used as a tool to quantify instrument identification in realistic musical excerpts and to inform the blending of instruments within sound mixtures. Our results show that neither spatial distribution nor reverberation had a significant effect on identification performance in simulated room acoustics, whereas sound quality ratings were clearly affected. In contrast, musical factors – including an instrument’s register, voice, and pitch – together with timbral features reflecting acoustic similarity, significantly affected identification. Highlighting the complex nature of music perception in natural orchestral scenes, these results suggest that musical instrument identification remains robust even under varying room-acoustic conditions. In other words, the acoustical richness of a scene such as the availability of spatial cues may not be directly beneficial for the accurate inference of musical sound sources but may be interpreted primarily to affect auditory “comfort” and thus judgments of sound quality. It remains to be consolidated whether these two aspects of music perception, ASA and the perception of sound quality, are two sides of the same coin or constitute separate dimensions of musical experience.

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